

WHAT ARE THE PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF E-GOVERNMENT SERVICES?

S'MANGELE FAVORITE DUMA¹ and LAWRENCE MPELE LEKHANYA²

^{1,2}The Department of Public Management and Economics, The Faculty of Management Sciences, Durban University of Technology, Durban, South Africa.

Email: ¹21225108@dut.ac.za, ²Lawrencel@dut.ac.za

Abstract

E-government is increasingly vital in modern governance, offering opportunities for improved service delivery, transparency, and citizen participation. In South Africa, however, implementation faces persistent challenges such as infrastructural gaps, socio-economic divides, and low digital literacy. This study seeks to examine public perceptions of e-government services in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as its guiding framework. It explores how perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) influence behavioural intention and adoption of e-government platforms, while considering contextual barriers affecting digital uptake. The study adopted a quantitative design anchored in TAM. Data were collected from 342 respondents across selected areas of KZN. Descriptive statistics, regression modelling, and factor analysis were performed using SPSS to test relationships between TAM constructs and e-government adoption. Findings show that citizens are more likely to use services such as SARS eFiling, GovChat, and eHomeAffairs when they perceive them as useful and easy to use. These platforms save time, reduce queues, and increase convenience. However, adoption is limited by poor internet connectivity, load shedding, complicated designs, and the dominance of English, which excludes many isiZulu speakers. While citizens value the potential of e-government, barriers hinder widespread usage. E-government can transform service delivery in KZN, but success depends on simplifying platforms, addressing infrastructural challenges, and ensuring inclusivity. The study demonstrates how TAM explains e-government adoption in KZN, highlights PU and PEOU as key drivers, and provides policymakers with practical strategies for more inclusive and effective digital governance.

Keywords: E-government; KwaZulu-Natal; Technology Acceptance Model (TAM); Perceived Usefulness; Perceived Ease of Use; Digital Divide; Trust; South Africa; Citizen Adoption.

INTRODUCTION

In this era of accelerating technological advancement, governments are under increasing pressure globally, to transition from traditional service delivery to digital platforms. This transformation is largely driven by the need for greater efficiency, transparency, accountability, and public engagement. E-government has become a core contemporary governance reform element. The broad definition of e-government is the use of digital technologies—particularly tools that are internetbased—in providing public services and engage citizens, as well as enhance administrative efficiency (Estevez & Janowski 2013; Gil-García 2012). In South Africa (SA), there is recognition of e-government as a strategic mechanism able to advance delivery of public services along with inclusive government services access. The function of information and communication technologies (ICTs) pertaining to public sector transformation is outlined in the National Development Plan (NDP) (2030), which states this is achievable through enhanced democratic accountability, and in fostering socio-economic development (National Planning Commission 2012). However, notwithstanding significant ICT

infrastructure investment and digital policy frameworks, uneven e-government services uptake and use is evident, particularly in provinces such as KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), where infrastructural inequalities, language diversity, digital literacy gaps, and public trust deficits persist (Bwalya, Mutula, & Sebina 2022; Stats SA 2022).

E-government in KZN must, therefore, be studied within this multi-layered context of digital divide, infrastructural underdevelopment, socio-political history, and diverse user needs. Without addressing these contextual nuances, e-government platforms are likely to exacerbate existing inequalities rather than alleviate them (Ngidi & Thakur 2020). It becomes critical then, to evaluate public perception—how citizens experience, interpret, and interact with digital services—as a lens for understanding adoption behaviour. The study answers this call by exploring how KZN residents perceive e-government platforms, what influences their engagement or disengagement, and how these insights can inform the design of a more inclusive digital governance framework.

This study explores public perceptions regarding e-government services in KZN in order that key adoption factors could be identified, the awareness and understanding levels among citizens assessed, and a contextual model developed that can guide more inclusive and effective e-government implementation in the province. By focusing on selected areas within KZN—namely Durban, North Coast, and South Coast—this research provides localised insights into a national digital transformation agenda.

Aims and Objectives

The study aims to examine public perceptions connected with e-government services in KZN and to determine which factors motivate adoption and use. One of the objective that guided the study was the following:

Objective

- To assess the factors affecting e-government operation and adoption in KZN.

LITERATURE REVIEW

E-government in the South African and KZN context

SA has made notable strides in promoting e-government, with platforms such as eFiling (SARS), GovChat, and the Companies and Intellectual Property Commission (CIPC) business registration portals leading the way. However, adoption across provinces is uneven due to infrastructural disparities, digital literacy gaps, and socio-economic conditions. KZN, as one of the most populous and diverse provinces, reflects both the potential in implementation of e-government, as along with its challenges.

Statistics SA (Stats SA) reports acceptance of e-government tools and their use in urban centres such as Durban has been relatively higher, due to better infrastructure and digital exposure. In contrast, rural and peri-urban areas across the North and South Coasts experience challenges, including unstable connectivity, limited device access, and language or literacy barriers (Stats SA 2023). Additionally, loadshedding and cyber-related concerns further affect user trust and

system reliability. Several local government departments in KZN have launched initiatives such as online billing for municipal services and digital platforms for housing applications. However, awareness, user training, and accessibility remain limited, specifically populations that are older as well as those in remote locations. There is thus a need for locally contextualised research to be familiar with how various factors affect e-government engagement in KZN.

Factors affecting e-government adoption in KZN

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Davis (1989) to explain user adoption of information technology. It remains one of the most influential theoretical frameworks in technology adoption research due to its simplicity and predictive strength. According to TAM, an individual's behavioural intention (BI) to use a system is primarily influenced by two constructs: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU). These constructs interact, as systems that are perceived to be easy to use are also more likely to be judged as useful (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

In the context of e-government, TAM helps explain how citizens evaluate and decide whether to adopt digital services, based on their expectations of effort and benefit. This is particularly relevant in South Africa, and specifically KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), where exposure to digital technologies varies widely across socio-economic, generational, and rural–urban divides (Govender & Marsden, 2022). In such settings, perceptions of usefulness and ease of use are critical determinants of adoption, as citizens weigh the potential advantages of digital platforms against infrastructural and social barriers.

Behavioural Intention (BI)

Behavioural Intention (BI) refers to an individual's conscious decision or motivational readiness to engage in a specific behaviour—in this case, the use of e-government services. Within technology adoption frameworks such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), BI is widely recognised as the strongest predictor of actual system use (Ajzen, 1991; Venkatesh et al., 2003). BI therefore acts as a critical link between perceptions of a system—such as Perceived Usefulness (PU), Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), and trust—and the actual behaviour of engaging with digital platforms.

In the e-government context of KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), BI is shaped not only by individual perceptions but also by broader personal and contextual factors, including digital literacy, prior user experiences, trust in government institutions, and prevailing social expectations. For example, even when online services such as SARS eFiling, eHomeAffairs, or GovChat are available, citizens may avoid them if they lack the confidence, skills, or belief that these platforms will be beneficial.

Research in developing countries shows that BI is highly sensitive to system quality and reliability. Poor experiences—such as incomplete transactions, website crashes, or inadequate support—often reduce users' willingness to try again, even when technical improvements are

later introduced (Bwalya et al., 2022; Alomari & Sandhu, 2023). This underscores that adoption is not only a matter of infrastructure but also of building consistent, trustworthy experiences that motivate repeat use.

For KZN, fostering BI requires more than simply deploying functional platforms. Continuous user engagement, awareness campaigns, and inclusive system design are needed to create positive expectations around digital service delivery. When citizens perceive clear benefits and feel confident in their ability to use these systems, their behavioural intention—and ultimately actual adoption—will be strengthened.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

PEOU refers to the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system will be free of effort (Davis, 1989). In practice, this means that government websites or mobile applications must be intuitive, accessible, and simple to navigate for citizens to embrace them. Research shows that when citizens perceive digital platforms as complicated, adoption rates decline sharply (Al-Shafi & Weerakkody, 2010; Almarashdeh, 2020).

In KZN, PEOU is especially important given the challenges of digital literacy and language diversity. Many users, particularly those in rural areas, struggle with overly complex systems that require advanced technical knowledge. For instance, when municipal billing systems or grant application portals lack mobile optimisation, multilingual support, or basic user guidance, citizens are less likely to engage with them (Nkohkwo & Islam, 2013). Conversely, platforms that are mobile-friendly and available in isiZulu are more likely to improve adoption, since they lower the effort required for interaction.

Recent studies emphasise that usability and inclusivity are central to building digital trust and ensuring widespread e-government adoption (Abu-Shanab, 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2021). Enhancing PEOU, therefore, requires not only technical simplicity but also culturally relevant design, multilingual accessibility, and continuous user support.

Perceived Usefulness (PU)

PU is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that using a system will improve their performance or offer a tangible benefit (Davis, 1989). In e-government contexts, PU reflects whether citizens see value in using online platforms for services such as tax submissions, ID or passport applications, social grant updates, and municipal service reporting.

In KZN, PU is closely linked to efficiency and reliability. When digital systems operate smoothly—enabling citizens to complete tasks without repeated visits to government offices—citizens perceive high usefulness (Makhubele & Ngoepe, 2021). However, experiences of frequent system downtime, incomplete transactions, or slow responses reduce perceptions of usefulness, undermining adoption.

Empirical evidence shows that PU often has a stronger impact on adoption than PEOU, particularly in developing countries where citizens prioritise tangible benefits such as saving time, avoiding long queues, and reducing travel costs (Alshehri, Drew & Alghamdi, 2012; Alomari & Sandhu, 2023). This indicates that while ease of use is essential, the ultimate driver

of adoption lies in demonstrating clear, practical value to citizens. For KZN, this means that e-government platforms must not only be user-friendly but also consistently deliver real benefits. Services that meet urgent needs—such as faster grant applications, accessible health information, or simplified municipal billing—are more likely to be embraced by citizens, thereby reinforcing the practical relevance of PU as a predictor of behavioural intention.

E-government implementation challenges in SA /KZN

Notwithstanding the strategic importance afforded to e-government in improving service delivery and governance, several persistent challenges undermine its effective implementation in SA, particularly in KZN.

Loadshedding

The persistent issue of loadshedding is among the most pressing challenges in infrastructure to e-government implementation in KZN, where loadshedding refers to the scheduled rolling blackouts implemented to manage electricity shortages. The national power crisis has led to frequent and unpredictable disruptions in electricity supply, severely impacting both citizens' ability to access digital services and government capacity to maintain service continuity. As Mutula (2021) points out, any form of digital transformation requires consistent access to electricity as a fundamental prerequisite, particularly in public service delivery.

In areas affected by loadshedding, citizens are often unable to connect to the internet, charge devices, or access online government portals. For service centres reliant on stable electricity to power routers, computers, and service databases, loadshedding results in delays, downtimes, and service interruptions. This is particularly critical in rural and peri-urban areas of KZN, where backup infrastructure such as generators or uninterrupted power supply (UPS) units may not be in place.

The unpredictable nature of power outages, furthermore, weakens trust in the reliability of e-government systems. As emphasised by Bélanger and Carter (2008) and Janssen *et al.* (2021), for digital public services to succeed, user trust in system stability and service availability is fundamental. When citizens repeatedly experience failed transactions or inaccessible platforms due to power issues, their confidence in the system deteriorates.

Loadshedding thus poses not only a logistical but also an institutional and psychological barrier. Addressing this issue requires integrated planning between national energy providers and digital governance bodies to ensure contingency mechanisms are in place, such as offline access options, mobile alternatives, and power backups in service delivery points.

Language Barriers and Multilingual Service Design

Language has a central function in e-government services access and usability. SA has 11 official languages, with isiZulu being the most widely spoken language in KZN. However, most government websites and digital portals are primarily offered in English, marginalising non-English-speaking citizens (Ntshakala 2021). This language gap limits comprehension and increases user frustration, more specifically among older adults and those with limited formal education.

International studies emphasise the importance in linguistically and culturally localising e-government content to enhance user engagement (Bwalya & Mutula 2015). In multilingual regions such as KZN, failing to offer services in local languages creates exclusion and undermines digital citizenship. To address this, governments must invest in language-localised platforms, automated translation tools, and community-based digital literacy campaigns that align with local dialects and communication norms.

ICT Skills amongst Citizens of KZN and Complicated Designs

A major challenge to e-government adoption in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) is the uneven level of ICT skills among citizens. Digital literacy in the province is highly fragmented, with significant divides between rural and urban areas, older and younger generations, and high- and low-income groups. Many citizens, particularly in rural communities, lack the basic computer or smartphone skills needed to access online services such as **SARS eFiling**, **eHomeAffairs**, or municipal billing systems (Govender & Marsden, 2022). This lack of skills means that even when infrastructure is available, citizens often struggle to make effective use of digital platforms.

The problem is compounded when government platforms are designed in ways that are overly complex, text-heavy, or only available in English. Complicated designs increase the cognitive effort required to navigate services, discouraging less digitally literate users from engaging with them. For instance, platforms that lack **isiZulu translations**, are not **mobile-friendly**, or require repeated logins can alienate large segments of the population who already face challenges in digital environments (Nkohkwo & Islam, 2013; Kassen, 2022). In these cases, the barrier is not only technical but also psychological, as citizens lose confidence in their ability to use the services successfully.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), originally developed by Davis (1989), has become one of the most widely applied theoretical frameworks for examining the acceptance and use of information systems. The model rests on the premise that two primary perceptions—Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)—determine an individual's behavioural intention to use technology, which in turn predicts actual system adoption. PU refers to the extent to which an individual believes that using a system will enhance their performance or improve outcomes, while PEOU denotes the degree to which a person believes that using the system will be free from effort (Davis, 1989).

In the context of e-government, TAM has been frequently employed to assess citizens' willingness to adopt online services such as tax filing, licence renewals, and social grant applications. Recent studies emphasise that PU is often a stronger predictor of adoption in developing countries, as citizens are more likely to use e-government platforms when they perceive tangible benefits such as time savings, reduced travel costs, and improved access to services (Alomari & Sandhu, 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2021). Similarly, PEOU plays a critical role in contexts where digital literacy levels are uneven, such as KwaZulu-Natal, where many

citizens face barriers related to language, education, and access to reliable internet infrastructure (Govender & Marsden, 2022).

TAM has evolved over time, with extensions such as TAM2 and TAM3 incorporating additional constructs like social influence, facilitating conditions, and trust. However, its core components remain central in technology adoption research. For e-government studies, TAM is particularly useful because it simplifies complex behavioural processes into two primary dimensions that can be empirically measured and tested. By focusing on PU and PEOU, policymakers and system designers can gain insights into how digital platforms should be designed to encourage citizen uptake, especially in regions with pronounced socio-economic inequalities (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008; Almarashdeh, 2020).

In this study, TAM provides the theoretical foundation for exploring citizens' adoption of e-government services in KwaZulu-Natal. It is employed to assess whether citizens perceive these services as both useful and easy to use, and how these perceptions shape behavioural intention and actual usage. This theoretical lens is particularly relevant in South Africa, where infrastructural limitations, language barriers, and trust deficits complicate the digital transformation agenda. Thus, TAM not only guides the analytical framework of the research but also offers practical direction for designing user-friendly, citizen-centred e-government platforms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a **quantitative research methodology** using a **survey research design** to address the research objectives. The approach was considered appropriate for collecting standardised data from a relatively large sample and for enabling statistical analysis of relationships among Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) constructs, namely **Perceived Usefulness (PU)**, **Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)**, and **Behavioural Intention (BI)** (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

A **non-probability sampling method, combining stratified and convenience sampling**, was employed to select respondents from three major regions of KwaZulu-Natal: **Durban, the North Coast, and the South Coast**. These areas were chosen because they reflect the province's socio-economic diversity and highlight differences in access to digital infrastructure. Durban, as an urban hub, has relatively high connectivity and exposure to online platforms, while the North and South Coasts include rural and peri-urban settlements where citizens face barriers such as limited infrastructure, load shedding, and digital literacy gaps (Govender & Marsden, 2022).

The **target population** consisted of adult residents of KwaZulu-Natal eligible to use government digital services, such as **SARS eFiling, eHomeAffairs, and GovChat**. From a total population of 355 individuals, **342 respondents** participated in the survey, representing a high response rate of 96.3%. The survey instrument was a **structured questionnaire**, designed around TAM constructs and informed by prior literature on e-government adoption. Responses were captured using a **5-point Likert scale**, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

agree.” This design ensured the collection of valid and reliable data on citizens’ perceptions of usefulness, ease of use, and behavioural intention toward e-government services.

The collected data were analysed using the **Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 29.0**. Both **descriptive and inferential statistical techniques** were applied. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, summarised respondents’ demographic profiles and general perceptions. Inferential statistics, including regression modelling and factor analysis, were employed to test relationships between TAM constructs and citizens’ behavioural intentions to adopt e-government services.

To ensure ethical compliance, the study adhered to the **Durban University of Technology’s research ethics guidelines**. Participants received an information sheet outlining the purpose of the study, their rights, and assurances of confidentiality. They were also provided with an informed consent form, which highlighted voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study presents the results of the analysis in a structured manner, aligning each set of findings with the TAM framework. The outcomes provide critical insights into citizens’ perceptions of digital governance in KwaZulu-Natal and serve as the foundation for the discussion and practical recommendations that follow.

Table 1: I find e-government easy to use for any activity

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	2	0,6	0,6	0,6
Disagree	40	11,7	11,7	12,3
Neutral	24	7,0	7,0	19,3
Agree	87	25,4	25,4	44,7
Strongly Agree	189	55,3	55,3	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

As shown in Table 1, respondents indicated a strongly positive perception of e-government usability, with 87 respondents (25.4 percent) agreeing and 189 (55.3 percent) strongly agreeing, making up a substantial 80.7 percent of the sample. This indicates the majority users consider e-government platforms as user-friendly and accessible, which is a crucial factor in the success of digital service adoption. According to Venkatesh *et al.* (2003), PEOU is one core technology acceptance determinant, and when users find systems intuitive and simple, their continued usage likelihood increases significantly. A smaller respondent group was neutral (24; seven percent), suggesting some ambivalence or limited interaction with e-government systems. Nevertheless, 40 respondents (11.7 percent) disagreed and two (0.6 percent) strongly disagreed, showing a minority users still experience usability challenges. The findings support research by Alomari (2020), which emphasises the significance of design simplicity, accessibility, and user support in enhancing citizen engagement with e-government platforms. Moreover, Dwivedi *et al.* (2021) argue government systems must prioritise inclusive digital experiences to cater to users with varying digital literacy levels.

Table 2: I find interaction with e-government less understandable

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	98	28,7	28,7	28,7
Disagree	144	42,1	42,1	70,8
Neutral	67	19,6	19,6	90,4
Agree	19	5,6	5,6	95,9
Strongly Agree	14	4,1	4,1	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

Results in Table 2 illustrate most respondents strongly disagreed (98; 28.7 percent) or disagreed (144; 42.1 percent), indicating 70.8 percent users find e-government system interactions clear and easy to comprehend. This reflects a generally positive perception of e-government platform clarity, structure, and usability. Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) identified perceived ease of understanding as among the key technology acceptance determinants, which directly affects user engagement and satisfaction. Well-structured systems that communicate processes clearly are more likely to be trusted and adopted by citizens.

A notable proportion users remained neutral (67; 19.6 percent), which may suggest they have experienced both understandable and unclear interactions or have not used the platform enough to form a strong opinion. Only a small minority indicated agreement (19; 5.6 percent) or strong agreement (14; 4.1 percent) with regard to the statement, suggesting a limited group finds e-government platforms difficult to understand. This aligns with Alomari (2020), whose findings stress although digital government platforms are improving in terms of user-centred design, continued investment in interface clarity, multilingual options, and user guidance features is essential to support citizens with varying digital literacy levels.

Table 3: I find e-government as e-resources that improve efficiency

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	5	1,5	28,7	1,5
Disagree	4	1,2	1,2	2,6
Neutral	31	9,1	9,1	11,7
Agree	131	38,3	38,3	50,0
Strongly Agree	171	50,0	50,0	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

In Table 3, the data clearly indicate strong support for the efficiency of e-government platforms, with 131 respondents (38.3 percent) agreeing and 171 (50.0 percent) strongly agreeing, accounting for a significant 88.3 percent total responses. This overwhelming positive sentiment suggests users perceive e-government systems as effective tools for streamlining processes, reducing bureaucratic delays, and improving access to services. According to Shareef *et al.* (2011a), perceived efficiency is a key driver of e-government acceptance, as citizens are more inclined to use digital public services when they save time and effort, compared to traditional government interactions.

A smaller respondent proportion was neutral (31; 9.1 percent), indicating even though they may not view e-government as inefficient, they may lack sufficient experience or evidence to fully

endorse its benefits. Only four respondents (1.2 percent) disagreed and five (1.5 percent) strongly disagreed, reflecting minimal scepticism regarding e-government service efficiency. This pattern aligns with the findings of Alomari (2020), who emphasises that citizen satisfaction increases when e-government platforms provide transparent, rapid, and user-friendly services that reduce administrative burdens.

Table 4: I find e-government provides faster online services for my needs

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
Disagree	0	0	0	0
Neutral	26	7,6	7,6	7,6
Agree	141	41,2	41,2	48,8
Strongly Agree	175	51,2	51,	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

The responses in Table 4 reflect very strong agreement with the efficiency of e-government platforms in delivering timely services. A combined total of 316 respondents (141 agreeing – 41.2 percent, and 175 strongly agreeing – 51.2 percent), or 92.4 percent, affirmed e-government platforms enable faster service delivery. This reflects positively on the perceived responsiveness and operational speed of digital government systems, aligning with Alomari (2020) in whose view perceived improvements in service efficiency and speed significantly influence e-government adoption.

Notably, no respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, and only 26 respondents (7.6 percent) remained neutral. The absence of negative responses suggests an exceptionally high satisfaction level with the promptness of services available through online government platforms. This concurs with findings by Shareef *et al.* (2011a), which argue one primary e-government acceptance driver is its ability to reduce time-consuming bureaucratic procedures and enhance convenience for citizens.

Table 5: I predict I will use e-government systems in the future

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
Disagree	1	0,3	0,3	0,3
Neutral	1	0,3	0,3	0,6
Agree	119	34,8	34,8	35,4
Strongly Agree	221	64,6	64,6	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

Table 5 show an overwhelmingly positive outlook toward future e-government adoption, with 119 respondents (34.8 percent) agreeing and a significant 221 (64.6 percent) strongly agreeing, totalling a striking 99.4 percent who foresee themselves using such systems. This high level of intention aligns with the BI concept in TAMs, particularly the UTAUT, where intention to use is a key predictor of actual usage (Venkatesh *et al.* 2022).

Only two respondents (0.6 percent) selected neutral or disagree, and none strongly disagreed, indicating virtually no resistance or uncertainty. This strong future intent suggests the respondents recognise the growing necessity and benefits of digital public services, including convenience, efficiency, and accessibility. According to Almarashdeh *et al.* (2023), high predictive intent in EU is often associated with increased digital literacy, improved trust in online platforms, and positive user experiences.

Table 6: I predict that I will use e-government systems to access public services

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
Disagree	0	0	0	0
Neutral	21	6,1	6,1	6,1
Agree	108	31,6	31,6	37,7
Strongly Agree	213	62,3	62,3	100,0
Total	342	100,0	100,0	

The results Table 6 depict indicate future use intention of e-government services as strong, with 108 respondents (31.6 percent) that agreed and a significant 213 respondents (62.3 percent) that strongly agreed, together accounting for 93.9 percent total responses. This overwhelming agreement reflects a widespread belief in the increasing relevance and utility of digital platforms for accessing public services. According to Almarashdeh *et al.* (2023), a high level of BI is a key indicator of eventual system usage and is strongly influenced by factors such as system usability, perceived benefits, and trust in digital governance.

Only 21 respondents (6.1 percent) remained neutral, while no participants disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting an absence of resistance or negativity toward future e-government systems use. This high acceptance level aligns with findings by Venkatesh *et al.* (2022), who emphasised that BI is the most significant predictor of actual system use in the UTAUT. Findings further suggest increasing digital readiness and growing public reliance on online government services as essential tools for engagement with the public sector.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirm that citizens in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) hold predominantly positive perceptions of e-government platforms. The high percentages of agreement regarding ease of use, efficiency, and speed of service delivery reflect strong support for the core constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), namely Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU). Respondents reported that platforms such as SARS eFiling, eHomeAffairs, and GovChat save time, reduce queues, and improve convenience, thereby demonstrating that citizens recognise the practical benefits of digital governance.

However, despite these positive perceptions, barriers such as poor connectivity, load shedding, limited ICT skills, and complicated designs continue to undermine adoption. These results reinforce previous studies in developing countries, which emphasise the dual role of technical efficiency and contextual constraints in shaping user behaviour (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021; Alomari, 2020). The significant behavioural intention to use e-government services in the future suggests

that citizens are willing to embrace digital transformation if platforms are made more reliable and accessible. The findings therefore highlight the importance of combining user-centred design with structural interventions. Simplifying system interfaces, offering multilingual support, and ensuring stable infrastructure are essential for sustaining adoption. This study contributes evidence that while TAM's constructs remain powerful predictors of adoption, contextual realities in South Africa — particularly infrastructural and socio-linguistic factors — must be integrated into models of digital governance.

Practical Implications

The findings of this study carry important practical implications for policymakers, system developers, and public administrators in KwaZulu-Natal and South Africa more broadly. The strong positive perceptions of e-government usability and efficiency suggest that citizens are ready and willing to adopt digital platforms, provided they remain accessible, reliable, and inclusive. To build on this foundation, government departments should prioritise **citizen-centred design**, ensuring that platforms are simple, mobile-friendly, and available in multiple local languages such as isiZulu to overcome literacy and accessibility barriers. Equally, targeted **digital literacy initiatives** delivered through schools, community centres, and local organisations are vital to equipping citizens with the skills needed to navigate online services confidently. At the same time, investment in infrastructure and system reliability is essential to minimise downtime and build public trust in digital channels. Public awareness campaigns can further encourage adoption by reaching citizens who remain neutral or uncertain about using e-government. Finally, stronger interdepartmental coordination will ensure that services are streamlined, avoiding duplication and enabling citizens to access multiple functions through a single, user-friendly portal. Collectively, these actions can strengthen adoption and ensure that the benefits of e-government are equitably distributed across the province.

Limitations

Although this study provides important insights into citizens' perceptions of e-government in KwaZulu-Natal, several limitations must be acknowledged. The research was confined to three regions of the province—Durban, the North Coast, and the South Coast—which, while diverse, may not fully represent the experiences of citizens in other South African provinces with different infrastructural or socio-economic conditions. The findings are based on self-reported perceptions, which are subject to bias, particularly where respondents may have limited direct experience with digital government platforms. In addition, the study applied the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as its guiding framework, which, although useful, does not capture wider contextual influences such as political trust, cultural values, or institutional responsiveness that could also affect adoption. Finally, the cross-sectional design provides only a snapshot in time, preventing the analysis of how perceptions and behaviours may evolve with ongoing technological and policy changes. These limitations suggest caution in generalising the findings and highlight the need for future research that incorporates longitudinal data, broader geographic coverage, and expanded theoretical perspectives.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that citizens in KwaZulu-Natal hold a strongly positive perception of e-government platforms, particularly in terms of **ease of use, clarity, efficiency, and speed of service delivery**. A large majority of respondents agreed that these systems are user-friendly and save time, which reinforces the **Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)** and **Perceived Usefulness (PU)** constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Importantly, behavioural intention to continue using e-government services in the future was exceptionally high, with over 90% of participants expressing confidence in their willingness to adopt these platforms. These results suggest that the groundwork for widespread e-government adoption in KZN is already in place. Citizens not only recognise the value of digital services but are also prepared to rely on them more in the future. However, the small proportion of respondents who reported usability challenges or expressed neutrality highlights the need for ongoing improvements. The lessons learned from this research are clear: to sustain and expand adoption, government must prioritise **user-centred design, multilingual support, and accessible platforms** that cater to citizens with varying levels of digital literacy.

The results further indicate that investment in **infrastructure reliability**, especially addressing load shedding and connectivity gaps, is essential to build trust and confidence in digital platforms. Ultimately, the study shows that when e-government systems are perceived as useful and easy to use, citizens are highly motivated to adopt them. This provides a valuable roadmap for policymakers and system designers to strengthen South Africa's digital governance and ensure inclusive service delivery.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to strengthen the adoption and sustainability of e-government in KwaZulu-Natal. First, government should adopt a **citizen-centred approach to digital platform design**, ensuring that systems are simple, intuitive, and multilingual, with isiZulu integration as a priority to improve inclusivity and accessibility. Second, **digital literacy programmes** should be expanded, targeting rural communities, older citizens, and other digitally marginalised groups through schools, libraries, community centres, and local organisations. These initiatives will help build user confidence and reduce digital exclusion. Third, continuous **investment in ICT infrastructure** is required to address persistent barriers such as unreliable internet connectivity, load shedding, and limited access in rural areas. This will enhance system reliability and build trust in online government services. Fourth, **awareness and communication campaigns** should be implemented to promote the benefits of e-government, ensuring that citizens are not only aware of available platforms but also understand how to use them effectively. Finally, stronger **interdepartmental coordination and policy alignment** are essential to create streamlined, integrated services, reducing duplication and allowing citizens to complete multiple tasks on a single platform. By implementing these recommendations, the provincial government can improve citizen adoption of e-government services and ensure that digital transformation contributes to more efficient, transparent, and inclusive governance.

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